

Design and Architecture for a Multi-Mode Pipelined, Floating-Point Adder

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February 5, 1991

Abstract - This paper presents the design and architecture of a VLSI floating-point adder (FPA). The multi-mode FPA is capable of both single-precision (32 bit) and double-precision (64 bit) arithmetic and was developed at the Air Force Institute of Technology (AFIT) using Complimentary Metal Oxide Semiconductor (CMOS) technology. The adder is designed for a 40 MHz clock using a pipelined architecture with a two-cycle latency. Area is minimized as hardware is shared for both single-precision and double-precision operations. Two single-precision operations in parallel are possible providing 80 MFLOPS operation. Double-precision operations yield 40 MFLOPS. With the exception of denormalized number representation, the FPA is fully compliant with the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers, Inc. (IEEE) Standard for Floating-Point Arithmetic (IEEE Std 754-1985). The FPA does not support the extended formats specified in IEEE Std 754-1985. In addition to floating-point operations, the FPA is capable of performing 32-bit integer operations. Five format conversions can be performed by the FPA on the four formats that are supported: single-precision, double-precision, integer and block floating-point. The block floating-point format supported by the FPA consists of an eight-bit two's complement integer representing the exponent for the block of numbers and 23-bit two's complement numbers for each mantissa.

1 Introduction

The design and architecture of this VLSI floating-point adder (FPA) was part of a master's thesis effort at the Air Force Institute of Technology (AFIT) [2]. The primary requirements to be met by the design of the FPA were:

1. Single- and double-precision floating-point capabilities
2. 40 MHz clock capability
3. CMOS logic
4. IEEE Std 754-1985 [4] compliance (as feasible)
5. Block floating-point to floating-point format conversion

The five requirements were met by the design. IEEE standard compliance was not fully attained as the FPA does not currently support denormalized numbers. In addition, the decision was made not to support the extended formats specified in the standard. An additional goal of the effort was to minimize area. The design and architecture used to meet these requirements and goal are presented in this paper. A floating-point multiplier (FPM) was also developed during the same time period by Capt Arnel Enriquez [1]. The near-term goal is to integrate both the FPA and the FPM into a single floating-point unit (FPU). This work was sponsored by the Air Force Rome Laboratories, Griffiss AFB, New York.

2 Architecture and Timing

The FPA consists of two primary sections: the exponent processing and the mantissa processing circuits. The block diagram of the FPA is provided in Figure 1. Each section is pipelined using single-phase parallel latches. Figure 2 shows the timing relationships for the mantissa section of the FPA. The clocking scheme employed uses a two-phase, non-overlapping clock as shown on the left side of Figure 2. The clock timing values shown are the current estimated values. The final timing relationships may vary somewhat based on actual requirements once the FPU is fabricated.

Figure 1: Floating-Point Adder Block Diagram

Figure 2: Pipeline Timing Diagram

A more conventional approach would involve the use of only two stages of pipeline latches using two-phase latches rather than the four stages using single-stage latches as shown in the figure. By breaking a two-phase latch apart, which is essentially done in the FPA, combinational logic can be placed in the "middle" of the two-phase latch. If a two-phase latch were used the first combinational logic circuit of a pipelined macrocell would not receive its inputs until ϕ_2 goes high. By using the single-phase latches within the FPU, the adder receives the inputs before the rise of ϕ_2 . This initial period of the timing diagram is where the largest benefit of using the current timing scheme is obtained. Within the FPU, the buses are driven by the registers beginning at the rise of ϕ_1 . Note in Figure 2 that the first logic block (Mantissa Alignment) has its outputs latched by ϕ_2 . Therefore, the first logic block has 15 ns minus the time required to drive the buses to complete its effort. It is estimated that approximately 7 ns are required by the bus structure. This leaves 8 ns for the first logic block to output the proper results. As a result, 8 ns are available for use by the FPA and FPM which would not have been available using two-phase latches. This 15 ns period is denoted on the timing diagram in Figure 2 by the letter "a."

The remainder of the timing logic works similarly. During the time period "b" of Figure 2, the Arithmetic Unit is performing its operations. Period "c" is used by the Incrementer/Rounding and Priority Encoder circuits while period "d" is required by the Output Alignment circuit. The final period, "e," is then used to drive the results onto the bus and to latch the results in the registers external to the FPA. There is time available in period "e" which could be used by the FPA as long as enough time is left to drive the buses. The block diagram shown is the actual configuration of the FPA. No additional FPA logic is needed in period "e" to meet the speed requirements.

The primary reason that the FPA design met the 40 MHz clock speed requirement was the design of an Optimized Carry Multiplexed (OCM) adder at AFIT. Capt Mike Scriber [6] completed the initial design on the OCM. As a class project, Capt Mike Irving [5] and one of the authors of this paper [3] further optimized the OCM adder. While Capt Scriber's analysis showed that the OCM would be capable of a 57-bit addition in 12 ns to 15 ns [6], these efforts reduced the time to 5.5 ns as demonstrated by SPICE simulations. The speed of the OCM enables the FPA to operate at 40 MHz with only a two-cycle latency pipeline.

3 Adder Operation

3.1 Single-Precision Mode

In single-precision mode, the FPA hardware is divided into two separate paths, one for the upper operand and one for the lower operand. For example, the exponent subtracter shown in Figure 1 is configured as two separate subtracters. By dividing the FPA hardware in this manner during single-precision operation, two additions can be performed in parallel without requiring much more hardware than would be needed for a dedicated double-precision adder. The discussion regarding operation in single-precision mode will be focused on only one set of operands, as both parallel paths are identical in operation.

The first action that must be performed is the subtraction of the exponents within the Exponent Subtracter. Since the IEEE standard specifies that the numbers are normalized, it is necessary to determine the difference of the numbers' magnitudes. The magnitude difference is needed since, prior to adding or subtracting the two numbers, the binary point of the two numbers must be set to the same absolute value. While each of the exponents have been biased in accordance with the standard, the bias need not be accounted for here since only the relative difference between the numbers is needed.

Once the difference between the exponents is known, one of the numbers must be shifted within the Mantissa Alignment Logic (if the difference does not equal zero) in order to align the binary points of the mantissas. This is accomplished by performing a logical right shift on the smallest of the two mantissas. The amount of shift is the value of the exponent difference. At the input to the right shifter, the "assumed 1" of the mantissa must first be inserted with the fraction.

At this point, the two numbers now have their binary points at the same absolute location and the numbers can either be added or subtracted within the Arithmetic Unit, depending on the operation selected. Once the proper operation is completed, the result is then rounded within the Incrementer/Rounding Logic (this circuit also performs the two's complement operation on negative results). The rounding mode is any one of the four modes as specified by the IEEE standard.

The final step to be taken is the normalization of the result. This requires shifting all of the leading zeros out of the mantissa within the Priority Encoder and then adjusting the exponent by the number shifted. The leading zeros are generated when a subtraction operation on two numbers of similar magnitude occurs. After this process, the most significant bit (MSB) is a

logic 1. This bit, however, is not returned as part of the result as only the fractional part is used in accordance with the IEEE standard.

As per the IEEE standard, the FPA performs comparisons between input operands and delivers the result to the FPU. Exception detection is also provided as required by the standard. The current version of the FPA does not support denormalized numbers, however, denormalized results are flagged properly as underflow exceptions.

3.2 Double-Precision Mode

The operations required in double-precision mode are identical to single-precision and, therefore, will not be detailed again here. In double-precision mode there is only one set of operands being operated on rather than the two sets in parallel as was the case in single-precision. In this case the adder hardware is configured such that the two halves of each circuit are combined to form single units. Again, this capability allows sharing of hardware between single-precision and double-precision modes, thereby reducing the amount of hardware needed.

3.3 Integer Mode

The format chosen for the FPA is 32-bit, two's complement numbers. Operation during integer mode is simple and straightforward. The exponent section is not used and the Mantissa Alignment Logic and Priority Encoder circuits of the mantissa section are disabled. The hardware used is the same as in floating-point modes, which again saves area. The only exception possible during integer operation is overflow and is correctly detected. No comparisons during the integer mode are provided.

4 Format Conversions

In addition to the three formats discussed previously (double-precision, single-precision and integer), an additional format which is supported by the FPA in terms of conversions is the block floating-point format. No addition or subtraction operations are possible directly with block floating-point, although the number may be converted to either single-precision, double-precision or integer for the operation. With this fourth format, it is possible to use the FPA to directly perform five different conversions. Four additional conversions are possible by using a two-step process which requires an additional conversion to an intermediate format. Table 1 presents the list of possible conversions and identifies which conversions can

be performed directly and which require a two-step conversion.

Table 1: Format Conversions

CONVERSION	DIRECT	TWO-STEP PROCESS
DP to SP	X	
SP to DP	X	
DP to integer		X
SP to integer	X	
integer to DP	X	
integer to SP		X
BFP to SP	X	
BFP to DP		X
BFP to integer		X

The conversion processes use both the exponent and mantissa sections of the FPA. For example, in performing a single-precision to double-precision conversion, the exponent must be converted from an 8-bit number to an 11-bit number as specified by the IEEE standard. The exponent subtractor is used to convert the exponent bias specified by the IEEE standard to the proper value. For this conversion, the mantissa is simply shifted to the left to provide the data out the proper bits and the rightmost bits are zero-filled. Other conversions are not quite as simple but are not detailed here due to space constraints.

As defined here, block floating-point numbers are "blocks" of numbers which have the same exponent value. The exponent value is not explicitly provided with each number; it is represented only once for the entire block. The exponent is an 8-bit two's complement number and is stored within an FPU register accessible to the FPA. The format chosen for the FPA is a 23-bit, two's complement number. The primary purpose of including block floating-point format within the FPA is to manipulate data from another AFIT project which uses that format. The mantissa length used in that project is only 23 bits and, therefore, the 23-bit capability of the FPA is sufficient. The initial plan was to provide a 32-bit block floating-point capability. The additional seven bits of capability, however, would have required a substantial increase in hardware.

5 Conclusions

All FPA requirements were met by the design. In addition, by cleverly sharing the hardware resources among the various modes, area was significantly decreased. The current status of the FPA is to fabricate the device soon.

References

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